

SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF METAPHOR IN ADVERTISEMENTS

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Annotation: This article discusses some aspects of the field of linguoculturology. In particular, some aspects of newspaper discourse are analyzed.

Keywords: source domain, economic discourse, politic discourse, target domain, concept, conceptsphere.

INTRODUCTION

The linguistic means are studied on the basis of the assumptions of the modern trends such as Psycholinguistics, Discourse Analysis, Linguocognitive and Linguocultural Studies. Thus, the present article is aimed at revealing metaphors in newspaper discourse and their classification in the light of Cognitive linguistics and Linguoculturology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Referring to the different scholars, we can outline the following interpretation of Linguoculturology: it is a complex and interdisciplinary study of the linguistic means which embody cultural and ethnical specificity. Cultural specificity and ethnic peculiarities are reflected both linguistically in the notional component of language unit and non-linguistically through its deep semantics. In this way, Linguoculturology is the discipline which by the use of systematic methods investigates the language units (linguoculturemes) that embody store and transfer culture and are usually revealed in discourse. [Ashurova 2012, Воробьев 2006, Красных 2002, Телия 1999]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among all types of culturally specific means, however, metaphor is of paramount importance. It is worth noting, that there are two approaches to its investigation: metaphor as a linguistic mechanism, and metaphor as a cognitive principle. The first mentioned approach presumes metaphor as a stylistic (rhetoric) device that is used for achieving poetic imagination and consequently making an aesthetic impact on the readers. In this case metaphor is the property of the language.

The second approach has initially been put forth by American linguists G. Lakoff and M. Johnson in their work "Metaphors We Live By". Having introduced the notion of conceptual metaphor they highlighted that it is "pervasive in everyday life, not just in language, but in thought and action. Our ordinary conceptual system, in terms of which we both think and act, is fundamentally metaphorical in nature" [Lakoff, Johnson 1980: 4]. In this way, we enlarge our conceptual system by acquiring the concepts through the conceptual metaphor. Thus, conceptual metaphor enabled scholars to study it not only as a stylistic device, but also as a phenomenon through which language and cognition are interrelated.

According to the theory conceptual metaphor is the cognitive process between two frames (structures of knowledge) – the source domain and the target domain. The source domain is the structure of already acquired notions whereas the target domain represents the new concepts that are going to be acquired. The acquisition of new concepts is realized through metaphorical mapping that transfers some of the elements from the source domain to the target domain. In other words, the source domain serves as a basement for the target domain, i.e. the new knowledge is acquired in comparison with the old one. As a matter of fact, some of the elements, and consequently some of the features, of the source and target domain implicitly coincide with each other. This coincidence was termed as invariance.

The assumption about the cognitive nature of metaphor and its cultural value goes back to the Aristotle's times; the philosopher claimed that metaphor is a conversion of the name from one kind to another by analogy [Аристотель 1927: 39]. Sh. Bally explains the metaphor as a way to compare substantial objects with the abstract ones by expressing the comparison within one sign [Балли 1961: 221]. Joining these views V.A. Maslova considers metaphor as a powerful tool for cognizing the abstract notions, which are more complicated in nature. The cognition is based on the comparison of the new (abstract) concepts with the old (concrete) ones. She adds that metaphor reflects fundamental cultural values as it embodies the nationally and culturally specific world outlook. [Маслова 2001: 90-91]. G. Lakoff highlights the fact that conceptual metaphor is an integral part of the cultural paradigm possessed by the native speaker [Lakoff 1993:210]. Thus, the acquisition of the new concepts is an effective means of enlarging the conceptsphere of the native speaker and consequently widening the national world picture.

There distinguished three types of conceptual metaphors: structural, ontological and orientational metaphors. Structural metaphor presupposes the acquisition of the concepts of the target domain by their systematic organization through the comparison with the everyday activities. Ontological metaphor is the way we perceive abstract notions by outlining their shapes in the space, or by personification. Finally, the orientational metaphor organizes the whole system of concepts with respect to one another. That is to say, the concepts of the target domain are organized according to our experience of spatial orientation. [Lakoff, Jonson 1980]

Conceptual metaphor is of frequent use in political discourse. Newspapers as one of its types present a great number of examples. It may probably be connected with the assumption that a person tends to react not so to objective reality as to the cognitive representations of the reality in his mind. Since the cognitive frames (knowledge structure) are usually formed by the means of metaphor, so it may be an effective tool to exert influence on the addressee and as a result on his actions [Будаев, Чудинов 2008:51]. In this way, by revealing source domain through metaphorical representation we may reveal the attitude of the addresser towards the issue being discussed.

To better understanding the political nature of conceptual metaphors and their functions in newspaper discourse, let us consider some of the examples taken from the Guardian newspaper:

Europe moves to end passport-free travel in migrant row

European nations moved to reverse decades of unfettered travel across the continent when a majority of EU governments agreed the need to reinstate national passport controls amid fears of a **flood of immigrants** fleeing the upheaval in North Africa.

Thousands of Bulgarians and Romanians 'plan to flood UK in 2014' as employment restrictions relax

Hordes of Romanians and Bulgarians are already preparing to head for Britain in search of work, according to a Mail on Sunday investigation.

The **immigration invasion** that never was. No extra flights, empty seats – the lack of stampeding Bulgarians and Romanians shows the right-wing hysteria for what it was.

The metaphorical expressions: **flood of immigrants, to flood UK, to head for Britain, immigration invasion** conceptually link with the image of invaders that form the structural metaphor – IMMIGRANTS ARE INVADERS.

Indeed, the immigration has become a sensitive topic for the British nowadays; as a consequence, their arrival is compared with invasion or even with the natural disasters. By using these metaphorical expressions the editors form a respective image in this way influencing the public opinion. Thus, the conceptual metaphor works towards cognition forming a certain concept in the readers' concept sphere through the image of INVADER.

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the article we have examined metaphor which is not only a stylistic device but also a complex cognitive process for cognizing the world and designating new concepts. It has been found that metaphor is closely connected with culture as a tool serving for widening the conceptual world picture. The conceptual metaphorisation in newspaper discourse is a two-fold process. It, on the one hand, is used to invoke certain concepts in the readers' conceptual frame, while, on the other, is used as the form of unique expressions aiming at creating new concepts and images for the sake of provoking certain pragmatic effect.

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